

Partial Discharge Diagnostic of High Voltage Power Cables with associated Accessories and the Human Experience for installation

Mostafa Mokhtar¹⁻², Emad Abdullah Mohammed Bawajih²,

Saudi Electricity Company, Saudi Arabia Kingdom¹⁻²

Adel ElFaraskoury³, Mohamed Muhanna⁴,

Extra High Voltage Research Center, Egyptian Electricity Holding Company, Egypt³

Faculty of Engineering, Al-Azhar University, Cairo, Egypt⁴

MMAhmad4@se.com.sa, Badr_power1429@yahoo.com

SUMMARY

Partial discharge (PD) measurement methods are most important and preferred in testing of underground high voltage cables and they have received much attention in recent years. Apparent charge, partial discharge inception voltage as well as number and distribution of PD pulses are most important quantities for the determination of the insulation quality. Identification with certain PD patterns and localization of PD are most important aspects. Different ways to suppress external noise is applied to detect signals with high sensitivity also in difficult on-site conditions. Partial discharge detection method can be classified into two techniques, conventional and un-conventional. Conventional PD detection is a standardized method for PD measurement as described in IEC 60270. This method based on measurement of apparent charge displacement q in the leads of the sample. This charge is usually expressed in pico-Coulombs (pC). Un-conventional PD measurement is based on detection of high frequency PD activities. In this paper an overview covering best practices for PD measuring using conventional and un-conventional methods is presented and predictive diagnostic programs to cable system is applied and the Human Experience Level for installation (Joints & Terminations) of the Power Cables. It contains also the results of many measurements carried out on XLPE cable system.

KEYWORDS

Partial Discharge-High voltage cables- Conventional and un-conventional- Cross bonding links-High frequency current transformers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Power cables are of great important in power transmission and distribution systems. Power cable system basically consists of cables themselves and their accessories. Cable accessories consist of joint and termination. Joint is special connection component which used to join two cable ends together while termination is special component to provide the end of a cable. The various aspects are considered while installing the cable termination and joints because they must possess the same integrity as their associated cables while making the connection both in all indoor and outdoor applications. Insulation of cable and accessories may be defected or deteriorated in installation and in use. After laying tests a diagnostic measurement should detect faults and defects caused by installation. Successful measurements give fingerprint for further diagnostics during the service of the cable system. Partial discharges are one of the major reasons for degradation of cable system insulations in service. Partial discharge measurement methods are most important and preferred and they have received much attention in recent years. Apparent charge, partial discharge inception voltage as well as number and distribution of PD pulses are most important quantities. Identification with certain PD patterns and localization of PD are most important aspects. Different ways to suppress external noise is applied to detect signals with high sensitivity also in difficult on-site conditions [1].

2 PD measuring system

After installation or long-time use, the insulation of cable or accessories may include small voids and cavities, conductive or insulating contaminants, or conductive protrusions in different interfaces. The installation may also cause other defects like mechanical cuts. During the service the temperature variation and other environmental stresses as well as electric filed and heating due to load current may enlarge these defects, and partial discharges may be incepted. These effects may also introduce cavities in originally sound cable insulation or enlarge original micro voids. Erosion by ion bombardment and chemical effects gradually change small defects to electrical trees with consequent final breakdown [1]. Partial discharge measurement methods are most important and preferred and they have received much attention in recent years. Apparent charge, partial discharge inception voltage as well as number and distribution of PD pulses are most important quantities. Identification with certain PD patterns and localization of PD are most important aspects. Different ways to suppress external noise is applied to detect signals with high sensitivity also in difficult on-site conditions. The measurements set-up of this work was built in partial discharge of by using coupling capacitor and on site by using High Frequency Current Transformer (HFCT). Several methods for set-up energizing and detection of PD will be used for investigation of installation defects. In this paper the experiment methods for energizing and PD detection are described.

3 Conventional PD detection method

Conventional PD detection method is standardized method based on international standard IEC 60270 [2]. Partial discharges that occur in the test object will produce current or voltage pulses. In contrast to the well-established PD measuring method according to IEC 60270 the described system operates in the UHF frequency domain, hence the derived and evaluated output PD pulse magnitude is more or less a measure of the PD current amplitude and not for the apparent charge as defined in the above-mentioned standard [3]. This method based on measurement of the charge displacement q , expressed in (pC), from the pulses which generated from partial discharge. Figure (1) shows the test set-up for 220kV test voltage and PD

measurements according to IEC 62067 [4]. In these PD measurements, 50Hz continuous AC voltage is used as an energizing method. The PD detector consists of several important components: regulator transformer, high voltage reactor, high voltage filter, coupling capacitor, digital universal measuring instrument and PD detector (TE571). Calibration of PD measuring instrument is important factor to ensure that the PD measuring system is able to measure the PD magnitude properly. Calibration is done by injecting a short duration current pulse of known charge from the calibrator to the terminal of test object while the measuring system is de-energized. Using this PD detector several important parameters of PD occurrence can be obtained such as:

- PD inception voltage (PDIV)
- PD magnitude in pC at PDIV
- PD magnitude as a function of voltage applied

4 Human Experience Level for Installation

4.1.1 for High Voltage Cable 220Kv

Figure 1: XLPE cable sample–1x1600mm²–220 kV with accessories test

In the shown the test setup for XLPE power cable 127/ 220kV –1x1600mm² approximately length 35 m with two different type of joint and termination for type test voltage according to IEC 62067. In these PD measurements, 50Hz continuous AC voltage is used as an energizing method. During the processing of the sample to a test type and fill the oil inside the cable termination, occurred bubbles led to the high magnitude of the partial discharge. PD measurement is carried out in 2 minutes for each test voltage. During this period three quantities are recorded: the number of PD pulses, the maximum value of PD magnitudes and the average value of PD magnitudes. for the cable termination 220 kV discussed and the display a 3–dimensional relationship between discharge magnitude, discharge intensity. there are more discharge quantities in the positive half of power voltage cycle than that in negative half. And the number of discharges in the positive half is more than that in the negative half. From the discharge phase–position distribution the number of pulses/second as observed during 2 minutes test time. the PD measurements results before oil degassing from termination recorded 7.5 nC and after oil degassing from termination recorded 2.8 pC as shown in figure1 and the PD measurements results as shown in Figure (2.1, 2.2).

Figure 2.1:3D distribution as obtained at 195 kV before & oil degassing

Figure 2.2:3D distribution as obtained at 195 kV after oil degassing

4.1.2 for Medium Voltage Cable 33 KV

Figure 3: cut off earth wire connecting in the stress cone of the termination for Cable 18/30kV-3x240mm²

PD magnitude for the cable sample 18/30 kV- 3 x 240 mm² with termination defect as a result of poor workmanship after heating cycle 160 hour, after change this termination. The sample shall be subjected to a partial discharge test at 1.73 U₀ don't exceed 5 pC according IEC 60520-2 but after heating cycle occur cutting of the earth wire stress cone witch connected end termination as figures (3)-(3.1)-(3.2)-(3.3) this case giving PD value greater than maximum limit when after repair the defect which occur of the earth wire stress cone for end termination the partial discharge test at 1.73 U₀ don't exceed the limit value 5 pC

Figure 3.1:3D distribution as obtained at 31 kV Ph. -R

Figure 3.2:3D distribution as obtained at 31 kV Ph. –B

Figure 3.3:3D distribution as obtained at 31 kV Ph. –C

5 Un-Conventional PD Detection Method

Un-conventional PD detection is used to provide result with suppressed noise or high signal to noise ratio. Basically, there are two main methods, the High Frequency/Very High Frequency/ Ultra High Frequency (HF/ VHF/ UHF) and acoustic method. Furthermore, HFCT method will be used for investigation of un-conventional PD detection in this paper. HFCT method at cross bonding box of 220 kV or earth wire of 66 kV for XLPE cable systems showed high sensitivity and calibration is possible using PD calibrator on the cable terminations, and another type of measuring by use of a coupling capacitor according IEC 60270 is based to PD detection of high frequency signal generated from PD activities. PD measuring equipment for un-conventional PD detection can be divided into several important sections: PD sensors, triggering parts, PD analysis system MPD540 and computer equipped with PD software as shown in Figure (4). Partial discharges measuring at Cross-Bonding (CB) links by using inductive sensors are especially designed as an inductive sensor, such installation is even possible under on-line conditions, as the sensor is a clamp-on HFCT that can be opened and clamped around a cross bonding link cable. Figure (5) shows the installed HFCT inside a cross-bonding links, also used PD gating unit for gating purposes in order to provide the possibility to filter certain external background noise. The PD sensitivity using HFCT the central measuring frequency is recommended to lie between 2 MHz and 10 MHz in a flat zone of the frequency spectrum. The spectrum is obtained from FFT of calibration PD pulses. Furthermore, the measuring frequency must be set in order to obtain the greatest possible PD signal/noise ratio. In addition, an "on-site performance check" must be carried for the selected measuring frequency before the PD measurement starts [6].

Figure 4: On-site PD measurements with coupling capacitor

Figure 5: CB Link with mounted three HFCT (PD Sensor)

The system consists of 3 single PD detection units at each phase of the cross-bonding box. For PD measurement at the cross-bonding box, the PD signal on each phase is detected by clamp-on type HFCT sensors. Each sensor output is connected to a PD measuring unit. The measuring unit is connected via a fiber optic cable to a notebook with PD acquisition and evaluation software for synchronous signal detection of all connected measuring units. Interrelated calibration of PD measuring unit is done by injecting a PD calibration pulse at one HFCT. Also, HFCT sensor is connected around the core of each phase of the cable as shown in the Figure (6) to measure both phase-to-phase and phase-to-earth PD activity in the cable and termination. This type of sensors mostly used in practice due to the advantage that this sensor does not disrupt the normal configuration of the accessories and cable part. For measurement at the cross-bonding box, the PD signal on each phase is detected by clamp-on type HFCT sensors. Each sensor output is connected to a PD measuring unit. The measuring unit is connected via a fiber optic cable to a notebook with PD acquisition and evaluation software for synchronous signal detection of all connected measuring units. Interrelated calibration of PD measuring unit will be done by injecting a PD calibration pulse at one of the HFCT and used an integrated PD gating unit for gating purposes in order to provide the possibility to filter certain external background noise [7].

Figure 6: Measurement set-up for PD detection using HFCT sensor around the earth wire of the 66kV cable

6 Test setup for on-site PD measurements

6.1 AC Cable systems testing after installation

The most important stress of a XLPE cable in service is the stress with the operational alternating voltage. Consequently, the most favored on-site test voltage of power frequency, standardized for laboratory testing in the range from 45 to 50 Hz. But for on-site testing a larger frequency range is being discussed. The on-site testing of cables has to check the insulation condition after-laying and assembly of cable system, as well as ageing of cables and accessories, since the performance of the cables and accessories was tested during the type and routine tests in the factory. The after laying test of new cables fills the quality assurance gap between the type and routine tests of the cable at the manufactures site and the commissioning of the complete cable system on-site. During the assembly or repair of a cable system, defects of the cable sheath and misassembled of joints and terminations can occur [8]. The tests have been carried out on-site according to IEC 60840 and IEC 62067. These standards offer alternative for AC test procedure, besides the testing voltage sinusoidal waveforms have the frequency between 20 Hz and 300 Hz. The voltage applied for 1 h, either with a voltage according $\sqrt{2} U_0$ or with $1.7 U_0$ depending on practical operational conditions, it is also possible to test with U_0 for 24 h [9,10] for 66 kV/220 kV cables (where U_0 is the per phase voltage). Therefore, the XLPE cable insulation was subjected to AC tests after assembling and at the same time partial discharge measurements were done on all accessories simultaneously for three-phase PD measurement on the relevant joint box, also the cross-bonding is changed to straight-through connection, to minimize cross-talk between the three phases and to clearly distinguish between the three joint of one group. By controlling the resonant circuit using capacitance and inductance elements the resonance occurs and the energy is absorbed at any instant by one reactive element within the system. The control of test system searches for the resonant frequency automatically and the HV test is carried out at this frequency.

6.2 Partial discharge measurement

Measuring of partial discharges is carried out using the MPD 540 measuring instruments with frequency tuned resonant test system as a source at the terminations and the clamp-on type High Frequency Current Transformer Sensors (HVCT) at cross bonding box of 220 kV for XLPE cable systems showed high sensitivity and calibration is possible using PD calibrator on the cable terminations, and another type of measuring by using of a coupling capacitor according to IEC 60270 is physically limited to a maximum detectable cable length of proximally 2 km becomes too low sensitivity, depending on cable parameters and PD background noise. Before applying the voltage, the noise level is measured and reached 20 pC. The partial discharges measurements by using Coupling Capacitor using conventional PD is shown in Figure (4) and with un-conventional PD is shown in Figures (5,6). The sensitivity of the partial discharge detector has to be modified until the detector shows the calibration charge. Partial discharge measurements carried out during HV tests, using a test sequence providing several increase the voltage in steps of 50 kV and observe the PD pattern at each voltage level. At $U_0 = 127$ kV take a PD-measurement recording during 1 minute and afterwards increase the voltage in further steps of 50 kV until 216 kV. At each step note the measured PD value. Once reaching 216kV leave this voltage applied for 1 hour and observes if there is a change in the recorded PD pattern and value, just before the 1-hour test period takes another recording of the PD measurement for 1 minute. While ramping the test voltage down, take another PD measurement for 1 minute at $U_0 = 127$ kV. The following test procedure shows in Figure (7). Although each single cable and accessory is subject to routine

tests at the manufacturer lab, transport, cable laying and installation can lead to unnoticed defects. External damages due to cable laying are usually detected by DC testing of the oversheath. In consequence, after-installation tests of the insulation can focus on defects in cable accessories, e.g. interfacial problems, improper positioning, cuts or scratches, contaminations etc. Such defects do not necessarily lead to breakdown within testing time, bearing the risk of breakdowns later in service. Sensitive on-site PD measurements significantly reduce this risk [11, 12, 13, and 16].

Figure 7: Withstand voltage for on-site AC test with partial discharge measurements

Detecting PD on long cables is a good start to the diagnosis of the system condition. However, it is only a start, and the obvious next stage after detection is to locate where the PD originated from. Once located, the final stage is to understand the problem which has generated the PD activity, and to make some sort of remediation plan which may include replacement of the offending cable or plant item. The combination of capacitive PD sensors and multichannel PD detection worked fine for tunnel-laid cable systems. But for direct buried cable systems, PD sensor coaxial cables bear the risk for tightness problems. In this case, the only alternative to dedicated PD sensors inside cable accessories is inductive PD detection at the Cross-Bonding (CB) link boxes, because these boxes are usually accessible. Long HV/EHV cable systems, where PD detection at the terminals cannot provide sufficient sensitivity, make use of CB to minimize losses. Inductive PD detection on CB links proved as a sensitive alternative for PD detection at the CB joints [13, 14, 15].

7 Test results and experience

Long HV and EHV cable systems are usually designed as cross-bonding systems to minimize screen losses and limit voltage rise. Using cross-bonding links for on-site PD measurements is suited for direct buried systems, has no impact on the cable systems, needs no PD sensors integrated in the cable joints, offers a low-cost solution and so opens a wider range of applications, in cable testing after installation as well as on service-aged or repaired cable systems [16].

Figure 8: PD measurements carried out during HV tests

The tests have been carried out on-site according to IEC for 66 kV / 220 kV cables system at 1.7 U₀ having different lengths to determine the faulty joints and cable defects. Therefore, the XLPE cable insulation was subjected to AC tests after assembling and at the same time partial discharge measurements were done on all accessories simultaneously for three-phase PD measurement on the relevant earth wire or joint box would be possible, also the cross-bonding can be changed to straight-through connection, to minimize cross-talk between the three phases and to clearly distinguish between the three joint of one group. The results of the on-site PD measurements with the alternating voltage of variable frequency (20 Hz – 300 Hz) have been performed in conjunction with test at cross-bonding links using HFCT sensors reported the discharge activity ranged from 11.69 pC to 683.4 pC as shown in Figure (8). The variation of noise level which is experienced during all measurements resulting in higher external interference from ends of the cable, also corona effect caused by floating parts close to high voltage at the cables termination with and without corona shield as shown in Figures (9). The on-site PD measuring level for cable system doesn't limit in the standards but depends primarily on the experience of those involved in the measurements, and the experience learned how to the diagnostics of the PD limit. We always ask this question from the manufacturers and owner customers, "What is the safe level for PD activity in the cable systems? The answer to this can only be, "there is no safe level for internal PD in the cable systems", all internal discharges will be damaging. The results of on-site PD measurements on this paper compare between conventional and un-conventional methods for different 66 kV/ 220 kV XLPE cable system have 500 m to 8Km length. Samples of the obtained results are shown in Figures (10, 11). PD Measurements of cable 66 kV by using coupling capacitor (CC) and HFCT sensors for 1.8 km long for the three phases are presented and figure 9 shows PD measurements of cables 66 kV by using coupling capacitor (CC) and HFCT sensors about 2.5 km long. PD activity of up to pC can be observed at the discharging joint. From Figures (12,13) it can be observed that there are some PD event originating in the termination at the remote end of the cable, in this way, PD pattern allows a view of the PD activity on the cable in a non-destructive. The level of the PD noise reduction depends on the kind of the noise, its frequency range, overlay of different frequency ranges, value of the noise amplitude and width. [17].

Figure 9: PD calibration and measurements from cross bond link without and with corona shield

Figure 10: PDM of cable 66 kV by using coupling capacitor (CC) and HFCT sensors for 1.8 km long

Figure 11: PDM of cables 66 kV by using coupling capacitor (CC) and HFCT sensors about 2.5 km long

Figure 12: PDM of cable 220 kV by using HFCT sensors for 8 km long

Figure 13: PD pattern for a joint at 127 kV

— Applied Voltage (kV) — PD Level (pC)

The results of on-site partial discharge measurements in pC for one joint by using HFCT sensor at 220 kV power cables are shown in the PD pattern by measuring at 127 kV, with choice mid frequency of 14 MHz as shown in Figure (14), and the curve is plotted from 0 Hz through 20 MHz.

Figure 14: Frequency pattern for PD measurements

8 Comparison (offline/online) for PD Measurements.

Figures 15: Comparison of (off line/on line) for PDM of the cable 66 kV-3 km by using HFCT sensors.

This case study the comparison between two on-site partial discharge measurements method for single core XLPE power cables 38/66 kV – 1x400 mm², approximately length 3km by using the HFCT sensors as shown in figures (15) The result of the PD monitoring shown, the combining the Low sensitivity on-line PD detection and High sensitivity off-line diagnosis can be of benefit by insulation condition assessment of distribution power cable networks. During off-line testing the cable under test is calibrated by sending and measuring a known signal. On the other hand, calibration during on-line testing is made by comparing the same signals measured at different locations alongside the cable length or by utilizing the noise. The length of the cable imposes limitation in off-line testing technique.

9 Defect of Workmanship after Installation of the terminations & joints

1-When testing for circuit 220 KV with stand test HV test carried out after installation $1.7 U_0 = 216$ kV for 1Hour according to IEC 62067 Many times, experienced has been cable systems having different lengths to determine the faulty joints after 15 min from test as shown in Figures (16).

Figure 16: Defect of Workmanship of the joints

2-When testing for circuit 220 KV with stand test HV test carried out after installation $1.7 U_0 = 216$ kV for 1Hour according to IEC 62067, has been cable Termination fault after 5min from test as shown in Figures (17)

Figure 17: Defect of Workmanship of the measurements

Many defects in Joints that cause partial discharges are there because of workmanship errors. Usually, the best results are achieved with good training. The most problematic part in termination is the point where the insulation screen is cut and stopped.

10 CAUSES OF CABLE FAILURES

Poor workmanship, Manufacturing, faults, Lightning strikes& over-voltage events, Ageing, Moisture, Overload, and Sheath corrosion, Overheat, Maintenance Failure Deferent Defect of Workmanship as shown in Figures (18,19)

Figure 18: Deferent Defect of Workmanship

Figure 19: Causes of Cables Failures

11 CONCLUSION

Two different partial discharge detection methods conventional and un-conventional are used for investigation, conventional IEC 60270 PD detection is applied by using PD detector with high voltage series resonant at frequency 50 Hz continuous, and the another method un-conventional PD detection is applied by using PD detector with HFCT sensor around earth wire or around the bar of cross bonding box for the long HV/EHV cables with variable frequency tuned resonant test system (20–300 Hz) have been gained in on-site test. The experiences show that the test voltage with U_0 for 24 hours is not feasible for incidence of failure after the test could be occurred. Also, the on-site withstand voltage test of XLPE cable systems with variable frequency test system (20–300Hz) combined with un-conventional PD detection is performed by using HFCT sensors after installation of HV/EHV cable systems reduces the risk from the service, also after repair the joint reassembling was done exactly in the same place given good results. Nevertheless, besides all routine and type tests before installation and the use of prefabricated and pretested accessories with conventional PD detection.

–If the workmanship doesn't have enough experience in installation of cables with accessories will give poor results in partial discharge therefore cable will be in risk to out of service.

–The on-site experiments showed that the partial discharge measurements by use of a coupling capacitor according IEC 60270 is physically limited to a maximum detectable cable length of proximally 2 km becomes too low sensitivity, depending on cable parameters and PD background noise, more than 2 km used the HFCT at cross bonding box of 220 KV, 66 kV for XLPE cable systems and around the earth wire of the cable 66 kV becomes too High sensitivity.

–As a result, combining the low sensitivity on-line PD detection and High sensitivity off-line diagnosis can be of benefit by insulation condition assessment of distribution power cable networks.

–Many defects in Joints that cause partial discharges are there because of workmanship errors. Usually, the best results are achieved with good training. The most problematic part in termination is the point where the insulation screen is cut and stopped.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to express his great thanks to the PD team work of the Extra High Voltage Research Centre and Saudi Electricity Company, Saudi Arabia Kingdom for providing their facilities during this work.

12 References

- [1] A. El Faraskoury "XLPE cables insulation ageing due to electrical partial discharge" Ph D Thesis, Cairo University 2011.
- [2] IEC 60270 "High voltage test techniques- partial discharge measurements" – 2000-12.
- [3] Werner Weissenberg, Toni Wunderlin, et al. " UHF- PD- Monitoring and On-Site Commissioning Test of 400 kV XLPE Insulated Cable Circuit at JEBEL ALI/ DUBI" Jicable 2007.
- [4] IEC Publ.62067 "Power cables with extruded insulation and their accessories for rated voltages above 150 kV ($U_m = 170$ kV) up to 500 kV ($U_m = 550$ kV) – Test methods and requirements", 2006-1.
- [5] K.Rethmeier, P.Mohaupt, et al, " New Studies on PD Measurements on MV Cable Systems at 50Hz and Sinusoidal 0.1 Hz (VLF) Test Voltage" CIGRE- May 2007.
- [6] F.Garnacho, I.Trasmonte et al., "On-site measurements experiences in insulation condition for medium and high voltage cables", CIGRE, D1-201, 2008.

- [7] A. El Faraskoury, F. Tahoun, M. Awad and O.E. Gouda "Investigation of partial discharge measurement for HV cable system with variable frequency" MEPCON'10, 128, Cairo 2010.
- [8] M. Awad, F. Tahoun, A. El. Faraskoury and O. Gouda "On-site Commissioning Test and Diagnostics of 220kV XLPE Cable System," CIGRE, B1.304, PARIS 2010.
- [8] IEC Publ. 60840, 3rd ed., "Power Cables with Extruded Insulation and Accessories for Rated Voltages above 30 kV ($U_m = 36$ kV) up to 150 kV ($U_m = 170$ kV) – Test Methods and requirements", 2004-4.
- [10] W. Weissenberg, F. Farid et al., "On-site PD detection at cross-bonding links of HV cables", CIGRE, B1-106, 2004.
- [11] E. Pultrum, E.F. Steennis, M.J.M. Van Riet, "Test after laying, diagnostic testing using partial discharge testing at site", CIGRE 1996, Session, paper 15/2/33-12
- [12] CIGRE WG 21.16, "Partial discharge detection in installed HV extruded cable systems", CIGRE 2001, technical report no. 182
- [13] E. Pultrum, S.A.M. Verhoeven, Testing of Extruded Cables experience in Type Testing, PQ Testing and Test After Installation, CIGRE 2004, paper B1-104.
- [14] C. Min, K. Urano et al., "Investigations of partial discharge measuring method via coaxial bonding wire for direct-buried power cable". T.IEE Japan, 121-B, No. 1, 2001.
- [15] Ulrich Herrmann, Andreas Kluge, Ronald Plath "After-Installation testing of HV/EHV extruded cable system- procedures and experiences" Jicable 2007.
- [16] C. Min, K. Urano et al., "Verification of partial discharge measuring method via coaxial bonding wire for direct-buried power cable". T.IEE Japan, 122 B, No.4, 2002.
- [17] Adel ElFaraskoury, Mostafa Mokhtar, Mohamed Mehanna, Ossama Gouda "Conventional and unconventional partial discharge detection methods in high voltage XLPE cable accessories" Advances in Electrical Engineering Systems (AEES), 2012, Vol. 1, No. 4 cable". T.IEE Japan, 122 B, No.4, 2002